

D6.3 REPORT ON PILOT DEMONSTRATOR GROUPS

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Lead Author (Org)	Najla Rettberg (RDA Europe)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Alexandra Delipalta (RDA Europe), Ari Asmi (RDA Europe)
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BoF	Birds of a Feather
RDA	Research Data Alliance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HEI	Higher Education Institution
TAB	RDA Technical Advisory Board
PID	Persistent Identifier
WG	Working Group
IG	Interest Group
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Executive Summary

This is a report on the achievements of the RDA TIGER pilots within the first year of the project. It gives a summary of the work carried out to date to support the pilot groups with the help of the RDA TIGER facilitator, and what services have been launched and employed. Finally it highlights feedback on the different services and lessons learned and ideas for moving on and refining the services. This deliverable should serve to assist the service owners about applying the services to the new WGs which are not part of the pilot and also assist other individuals or organisations in developing facilitation and support services in their work.

Table of contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	6
1.2 RDA TIGER Pilot Groups	7
1.1.1. Overview of where the groups are in their lifecycle	7
2. Status of the Groups to date	9
1. Community based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSPs)	9
2. Small Uncrewed Aircraft Vehicles (sUAV) and Autonomous Platforms Data	10
3. FAIRification of Genomic Annotations	10
4. Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)	11
5. National Persistent Identifiers Description (PIDs) Strategies	11
6. Global Open Research Commons (GORC)	12
3. Overview of the Services Used	14
‘F’ Services: Facilitation	14
‘A’ services: Landscape & Engagement Service	17
‘C’ services: Communication	17
3.1 Asana	20
4. Structured feedback and Testimonials	21
From the GORC WG	21
From the FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG	21
5. Lessons learned and Main challenges	22
Writing Case Statements.	22
Identifying Co-Chairs	22
Partner Engagement and International Engagement	23
Monitoring of Effort and Capacity	23
Overall Insights on the Pilot Groups	23

1. Introduction

The RDA TIGER project has taken a comprehensive approach to developing its Support Services for RDA Working Groups (WGs), by iteratively developing and refining the service offerings to the groups over the course of the project so far.

The principal approach has been to include six ‘pilots’ which were established as test-beds through which to launch the services at the start of the project. Before the grant preparation phase for RDA TIGER, potential RDA groups were identified for inclusion in the WP6 pilot programme, and six groups were approached and agreed to be included. They were chosen for a range of rationales: most of them were nascent groups with a concrete idea or data challenge, most had solid community backing, and a concrete plan for how to achieve the outputs. After the end of the first year of the project, all six are underway and are successfully adopting different TIGER services.

One person from the TIGER team, in most cases the project Facilitator, is allocated to work closely with the pilot groups and accompany them across their respective WG stages. The pilots themselves represent very different thematic areas around data sharing implementation. All, however, fulfil the strategic aims of RDA TIGER, which is to create outputs and RDA-endorsed recommendations for the benefit of the European and international data sharing and reuse landscape.

The work within both WP5 (Facilitation) and WP6 (Service Quality) started with an immediate learning curve in terms of initiating the TIGER services, and subsequently working closely with the pilot groups to implement the services. For four of the groups, the Facilitation service was the central starting service, with first actions to verify the idea and cultivate the community to get engaged with the group via the Engagement Service. This was followed by working with the groups to harness their communities and create a first draft of a Case Statement with a view to submitting this to the RDA’s Technical Advisory Board (TAB). Two of the groups are relatively mature in their Working Group activities, having established their Groups prior to the commencement of the TIGER project, and due to this the RDA TIGER team were able to initiate the Communication service. The work here feeds into the WP5 Facilitation Service and the Facilitation handbook. At the time of writing this deliverable, the pilots are still underway, although two have concluded most of their activities, as per their case statements.

1.2 RDA TIGER Pilot Groups

The following six WGs were chosen at the start of RDA TIGER and are described in detail in the following sections:

1. Community based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSPs)
2. Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data
3. FAIRification of Genomic Annotations
4. Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)
5. National Persistent Identifiers Description (PIDs) Strategies
6. Global Open Research Commons (GORC) Working Group

1.1.1. Overview of where the groups are in their lifecycle

Table 1. Groups and Service Requirements

Name of Pilot WG	Stage of WG	Service Targeted	WG START
Community based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers	Not yet endorsed by TAB	Facilitation 	
Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data	Not yet endorsed by TAB	Facilitation 	
FAIRification of Genomic Annotations	Not yet endorsed by TAB	Facilitation 	
Alignment on multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities	Not yet endorsed by TAB	Facilitation 	

National Persistent Identifiers Description (PIDs) Strategies	Finalisation and Output creation	Communication and Engagement FINALISATION	
Global Open Research Commons	Finalisation and Output creation	Communication and Engagement 8. Communication and Engagement	

2. Status of the Groups to date

All of the groups have been assigned an RDA TIGER representative (Facilitator or Communications Lead, depending on the needs they indicated). They have all either:

1. Established a clear scope of their WG;
2. Engaged a community to support the group;
3. Started a case statement, and/or;
4. Held virtual or in-person meetings.

Most groups have met in person taking advantage of [International Data Week](#) in October 2023 in Salzburg in order to underpin engagement of the group and to advance their goals and work plan and get commitment for the projected activities.

Below are brief summaries of WG activities so far in their life-cycles:

1. Community based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSPs)

Description: This group aims to better define the quality of services that support repository functions and activities, in turn developing a catalogue of requirements to allow those who provide these services to demonstrate their trustworthiness.

Status at the time of writing: The writing of the WG's case statement is in progress. A preliminary group membership is in place, with three meetings having taken place, including a session at the RDA Plenary 21 (P21) at International Data Week 2023.¹ Five co-Chairs from diverse geographies have been identified, which means the work can move ahead according to the RDA procedures.

Projected Outcomes of the group: The Working Group will produce a catalogue of requirements, providing a list of criteria to assess the trustworthiness of TRSPs.

Support provided by RDA TIGER:

- **Engagement:** Discussion with proposer of WG concept to elaborate how this WG develops previous work of Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership WG;² holding meetings to engage new members; identification and contact with potential candidates for co-chair positions.
- **Facilitation:** Planning and chairing of RDA P21 Birds of a Feather (BoF) meeting; drafting summary of P21 BoF discussion points; providing a review and feedback on draft case statement for co-chairs.
- **Communications:** Promotion of P21 BoF session; publishing blog updating RDA community of WG status and next steps.³

¹ www.rd-alliance.org/community-based-catalogue-requirements-trustworthy-technical-repository-service-providers

² www.rd-alliance.org/group/repository-audit-and-certification-dsa%E2%80%93wds-partnership-wg/outcomes/dsa-wds-partnership

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/blogs/p21-birds-feather-session.html>

2. Small Uncrewed Aircraft Vehicles (sUAV) and Autonomous Platforms Data

Description: This group aims to create specifications for drone services and resulting data for research and a demonstrator to show how these guidelines support the design and implementation of cloud-based infrastructures for Small Uncrewed Aircraft Vehicles (sUAV) and Autonomous Platforms data.

Current status: Preliminary meetings have been held with the two initial WG co-chairs, with plans to appoint at least one further co-chair. Case statement is currently being written to submit to the TAB in the first quarter of 2024.

Projected outcomes of the group: This is still under discussion, but it is likely to be in the lines of technical specifications for data and metadata best practices, focusing on interoperability with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and other virtual research environments (VREs).

Support provided by TIGER:

- **Engagement work:** Compiling a list of individuals/organisations whose work is relevant to WG;
- **Facilitation:** Organising and chairing a kick-off meeting which was attended by 23 participants and served as an excellent opportunity to brainstorm potential outcomes and the involvement of the wider community.
- **Communications:** Promotion of kick-off meeting.

3. FAIRification of Genomic Annotations

Description: The aim of this WG is to produce a global metadata exchange standard for genomic annotations (or “tracks”) and a set of services to bridge the gap between the requirements of analytical end-users/tool developers on one side and what is currently provided by the data producers/distributors on the other.

Current status: A [BoF meeting](#) was held at RDA P21, with approximately 20 in-person and virtual attendees. Prior to this, in September 2023, two kick-off meetings were held accommodating eastern and western hemisphere time zones, to which were invited data producers, tool developers and domain experts to discuss the initial vision for the WG. Three WG co-chairs are provisionally in place, with discussions ongoing with one potential further co-chair. The co-chairs aim to submit the WG Case Statement in early 2024.

Projected outcomes of the group: Among the proposed aims of the WG are a minimal FAIR metadata schema for genomic annotations, core infrastructure recommendations, and proof-of-concept adoptions of the core infrastructure recommendations.

Support provided by TIGER:

- **Engagement work:** There has been extensive community input to this group, which is well-connected internationally and within its discipline. Many initiatives have been flagged up to reach out to and it is a fully collaborative group which will mitigate any risk to repeating existing work. The WG is still looking for at least one more co-chair, with three provisionally in place.
- **Facilitation:** Organising and co-chairing kick-off meetings; co-chairing RDA P21 BoF session; on-going engagement with WG co-chairs and contact with new potential co-chairs; review of draft Case Statement and feedback.

- **Communications:** Promotion of kick-off meetings and BoF session; outreach to invitees.

4. Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)

Description: The WG intends to propose a methodology for the alignment of controlled vocabularies in multiple languages. The methodology will describe the various steps of the alignment process: selection of the controlled vocabularies, alignment through automated processes, manual curation and validation.

Current status: The WG held a kick-off meeting to disseminate the original concept for the WG and to elicit further engagement and contributions to the draft Case Statement from relevant individuals/organisations. The concept for the WG was presented by the proposer of the WG, Arnaud Gingold from OPERAS, at the RDA P21 session organised by the Vocabulary Services Interest Group.⁴ One co-chair currently in place with at least two others to be identified.

Projected outcomes of the group: Recommendations for creating and extending multilingual and multicultural vocabularies in the SSH; guidelines for FAIRifying and versioning of multilingual vocabularies.

Support provided by TIGER:

- **Engagement:** A community has been built which has agreed on the above aims of the group. geographical balance is still needed. One co-chair in place, with two more at least to be identified.
- **Landscape:** Desk-based research is currently underway to identify and initiate contact with relevant SSH controlled vocabulary developers, service providers, and repositories outside Europe.
- **Facilitation:** Organising and co-chairing kick-off session; ongoing work with co-chair to identify other potential co-chairs.
- **Communications:** Promotion of kick-off meeting and P21 presentation; outreach to invitees.

5. National Persistent Identifiers Description (PIDs) Strategies

Description: A well-established group in the finalisation stages of an effort to promote outputs.⁵

Final output: The final output is a guide and checklist for national development and implementation of PID strategies.⁶

Support provided by RDA TIGER:

- **Communications:** The RDA TIGER Communications service drafted a white paper on National PID Strategies, the WG's work and their output, also

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/international-data-week-2023-salzburg/building-collaborative-bridges-fostering>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg>

⁶ Simons, N., Brown, C., Bangert, D., & Sadler, S. (2023). National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist (Version 1.0). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091>

accompanied by an infographic based on the output.⁷ The paper was printed and distributed during IDW2023.

6. Global Open Research Commons (GORC)

Description: A well-established group in the finalisation stages of its group.⁸ The RDA TIGER Service have provided extensive Communication services and the final output

Final output: The final output is a model for considering essential elements of Commons during development and implementation.

Support provided by RDA TIGER:

- **Communications:** The RDA TIGER Communications service drafted two white papers on GORC⁹, the WG's work and their output, targeting the key audiences of policy-makers and implementers, as identified by the Group during extensive consultations. The papers were printed and distributed during IDW2023.

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/national-pid-strategies-wg/outcomes/rda-national-pid-strategies-guide-and-checklist>

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg>

⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/global-open-research-commons-international-model-final-output-and-supporting-documentation-available>

Figure 1: Overview of the RDA Working Group lifecycle and associated RDA TIGER services

3. Overview of the Services Used

Figure 2: Overview of RDA TIGER services

RDA TIGER utilises step-by-step processes in the implementation of the Support services for the WGs. RDA TIGER is developing four main services:

1. **Facilitation**
2. **Communications**
3. **Output Services**
4. **Landscape & Engagement**

The pilots were used to launch the services and the testing of the different elements involved, which the team initially developed in theory. Below, we highlight what actions were taken for the groups for each step of the services.¹⁰

'F' Services: Facilitation

The Facilitation Service is the core of the RDA TIGER project. Each Working Group receiving support from RDA TIGER is assigned a facilitator, on the basis of their domain knowledge and availability, who acts as the primary contact between the WG and the rest of the TIGER project. The facilitator supports WGs from initiation to finalisation phase. For the

¹⁰ see D5.1 for a full overview of the Facilitation services. Rettberg, N., Delipalta, A., & Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D5.1 Definition and handbook of the Facilitation Service (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096642>

Facilitation Service, this involved following the steps in the RDA TIGER deliverable, D5.1 “Definition and Handbook for the Facilitation Service”; further detail on the facilitator tasks and activities for each sub-stage can be found in this deliverable. Table 2 below outlines which Pilot group used which service.

Table 2: Overview of uptake of the Facilitation Service in the “F” Service stages

“F” Service	Sub-stages	Uptake by the Pilots
F1 Partner engagement Pilot groups who have used the service: All the pilots	<i>F1.1 Assigning the facilitator</i>	This has been the first step for all the groups. The groups have responded well to having a facilitator and all feedback has been positive.
	<i>F1.2 Inform WG members about the provided services</i>	The facilitator has shared a copy of the Facilitation Service Agreement.
F2 Work Plan creation Pilot groups who have used the service: All the pilots apart from the PID and GORC Groups	<i>F2.1 Internal Organisation of the WG</i>	For the following groups the concept of a WG has to be communicated, how it works and what are the processes that need to be followed. Groups who have used the service: All the pilots, apart from the PID and GORC groups.
	<i>F2.2 Draft Case Statement</i>	Four out of six pilots are currently writing their case statements to submit to TAB and for Community Review in early 2024. Groups who have used the service: All the pilots, apart from the PID and GORC groups.
	<i>F2.3 Create a work plan for the WG</i>	At this stage, the facilitator works with the WG co-chairs and members to lay out the plan for activities for the WG lifecycle, with details on how the Facilitation and other TIGER services can be used.

	<i>F2.4 Help to submit a support application</i>	Not applicable at this stage in the project, in the coming months this will be more relevant.
	<i>F2.5 Create a service agreement</i>	The facilitator has shared a copy of the Facilitation Service Agreement, which outlines the specific activities that a facilitator can take to support the WG. ¹¹
F3 Facilitation Service Support Pilot Groups who have used the service: All the pilots, apart from the PID and GORC groups.	<i>F3.1 Physical meeting organisation</i>	In each case a relevant facilitator was assigned to the pilots. In the case of the pilots it was the core team that took it on. For the new RDA WGs, Assessment of WG stage First meeting with the WG proposer/co-chair.
	<i>F3.2 Virtual meeting organisation</i>	The facilitator set up a kick-off meeting for all the four relevant groups, for example see the kick-meeting for the sUAV group. ¹²
	<i>F3.3 Facilitating Support Request preparation</i>	Not applicable at this stage in the project, in the coming months this will be more relevant.
	<i>F3.4 Internal management of the WG</i>	Ongoing in all the groups.
F4 Finalisation Services Pilot Groups who have used the service: The PID and GORC groups.	<i>F4.1 Last Mile support and Finalisation</i>	This part of the service is not yet valid as none of the groups have reached finalisation stage. For the PID and GORC groups, the focus here was at the end of the WG life-cycle but they used the 'C' service as their Recommendations and Outputs were in draft form when the TIGER support began.

¹¹ See Appendix 1 of Rettberg, N., Delipalta, A., & Asmi, A. (2023). RDA TIGER D5.1 Definition and handbook of the Facilitation Service (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096642>

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/new-rda-working-group-small-uncrewed-aircraft-and-autonomous-platforms-data-kick-meeting>

	<i>F4.2 Facilitating Output Maintenance Activities</i>	Not applicable at this stage in the project; in the coming months this will be more relevant.
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‘A’ services: Landscape & Engagement Service

The Landscape & Engagement Service is still in development but is particularly useful at the start of the WG to check that there is no overlap with existing RDA groups or other initiatives of the RDA TIGER partners. It also involves ‘qualitative’ engagement to discuss with the community the scope of the group.

For more on this, see D3.2 ‘Engagement Services Service Update’¹³ for an update on take up of the Engagement Service.

Table 3: Overview of uptake of the Engagement Service

‘A’ Service	Pilots
A1 Initial Landscaping	This was applied in particular to the following Groups in the ‘F’ phase. Groups who have used the service: All the pilots, apart from the PID and GORC groups.
A2: WG Landscaping monitoring	One group in particular used this: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alignment on multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).
A3: Landscape and engagement	This is a specific service more detailed in deliverable D3.2, which is the actual direct communications towards potential WG members or target audiences.

‘C’ services: Communication

The Communication Service provides tailored communications and dissemination services for supported WGs. This service is vital to ensure that the RDA and wider data community is aware of WG developments, to ensure there is no duplication of work, and to contribute to the overall awareness of relevant updates at each stage of the WGs. RDA TIGER can provide group-internal communication services where necessary, such as group webpage updates and maintenance, group mailing list management, communication tools management and provision (e.g., Slack, Google Drive, etc.), group meetings support (in

¹³ DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10444701

coordination with the senior facilitator), communication with the RDA Secretariat as and when needed. The RDA TIGER Communications team can also provide external communication services, such as group progress and general news dissemination within RDA with website posts, banners and sliders, news items and via the RDA Global newsletter, etc., external mailing list management (if applicable), RDA Plenary preparation support, graphic and collateral materials creation, and event management support (in coordination with the facilitator). As part of the initial discussions with the group, the Communications Service is available on demand. An important point to note is that Working Group activities concerned with the more outward facing aspects of the WG (e.g., engaging with RDA and other communities, organisation of webinars, etc.) require significant coordination between the Communications Service and Facilitation Service leads.

For the pilots, the communications effort has been taken up in the following ways, outlined below in Table 4.

Table 4: Overview of uptake of the Communication Service

"C" Service	Sub-stage	Pilots
<p>C1 Idea Dissemination Groups who have used the service: All the pilots, apart from the PID and GORC groups.</p>	<p><i>C1.1 Service request submission management</i> <i>C1.2 Coordination with the facilitator</i> <i>C1.3 Coordination with the application submitter</i> <i>C1.4 Creation of WG communication plan</i> <i>C1.5 Outreach to potential WG members</i></p>	<p>This was taken up to a large degree. For the four pilot groups, the kick-off meetings served as 'idea dissemination'. The initial ideas for the WGs were presented, as well as gauging community interest, inviting feedback and approaching co-chairs.</p>
<p>C2 Internal and External WG Communications Groups who have used the service: All groups.</p>	<p><i>C2.1 Coordination with the facilitator</i> <i>C2.2 Coordination with the WG</i> <i>C2.3 Creation of the WG Communication plan</i> <i>C2.4 Internal Communications Services</i> <i>C2.5 External Communications Service</i></p>	<p>This was the most heavily implemented Service area. The service available is a detailed template with a communications overview and a list of the contacts. For the pilots each group had a session with the Communications Service Lead. They brainstormed a provisional communications plan. The Communications Plan is where the Contact list also is most up to date and accurate.</p>

		The Contacts List is a critical element of the RDA TIGER Support Services.
<p>C3 Dissemination of Outputs Groups who have used the service: The PID and GORC groups used this service.</p>	<p><i>C3.1 Communication with the facilitator</i> <i>C3.2 Coordination of the WG</i> <i>C3.3 Creation or Update</i> <i>C3.4 Outputs and Adoption Promotion Services</i></p>	For many groups this is too early to comment on, as it was mostly employed by the pilot groups at the end of their life-cycle, the PID and GORC groups.

3.1 Asana

To enable a structured approach to managing the groups, the team has employed the use of Asana to track each step, along the lines of the facilitation life-cycle as defined in D5.1. Each step is logged and anyone from the TIGER project can get updates on the status of the WG.

4. Structured feedback and Testimonials

In preparation for this deliverable, the Pilots were surveyed and asked for feedback. One mechanism for this is the 'Feedback Form' for the groups. The questions asked are general and simple in approach. The responses can be submitted anonymously if the respondent wishes to do so. The team also sought in-person feedback from each group and below are some responses. This mixture of in-person interview feedback and feedback via the form has been effective to gauge what the groups value. In particular, the coordination of the group (largely "F3" services) features highly as a valued service.

From the GORC WG

"Despite our working group having started before RDA-TIGER, we have immensely benefited from their support. We first worked with RDA-TIGER to lead a workshop co-located with the 20th RDA Plenary, and it would not have been possible without their help and engagement. RDA-TIGER assisted with workshop planning, communications, hybrid logistics and support during the workshop, physical visual aid printing, and securing the room and catering. Both before and during the workshop, we also benefited from suggestions and ideas from RDA-TIGER on possible formats for our outputs to aid with their uptake in the community. We have barely scratched the surface of the skillset RDA-TIGER offers, and we're looking forward to working with them on facilitation of our working group as we move into work-intensive evaluations of our outputs to keep our members engaged, finessing our graphics, document writing and polishing, and our output dissemination strategy."

CJ Woodford, March 2023

From the FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG

The following feedback was received from the co-chair of the pilot group:

- "It takes time to get Facilitators on board, which slowed down the process.
- Once in place the Facilitator did a great job, he sent emails to many, leaving no corners unturned.
- Identifying co-chairs is hard. Many potential people are already at capacity.
- While minutes-taking is not the Facilitator's job, the group does request this. This could require domain knowledge but not necessarily.
- The most important part is to follow up on progress and help us to keep the momentum going and extremely important.
- The IDW P21 event [BoF event](#) provided a good useful in person session. Good contacts to others in the RDA community e.g., we met CTOs of infrastructures." **Sveinung Gundersen, October 2023**

“The support provided by the RDA-TIGER project has been a great benefit to our Working Group in the making. As initiator of the WG I started off with only a list of potentially interested members. There were no co-chairs in sight yet. The project provided crucial support to enable the WG to make a promising start. The support consisted of contributions to the draft case statement, the organisation of virtual meetings to discuss this case statement, the search for potential co-chairs and the preparation and running of the BoF session at IDW. All of this would not have been doable by me alone.”

Ingrid Dillo, December 2023

5. Lessons learned and Main challenges

Writing Case Statements.

Every new group has to submit a Case Statement for RDA Community Review and to the RDA TAB.¹⁴ This requires agreeing on a vision for the group and each group needs to provide a detailed plan of work. The RDA Case Statement template was provided by the facilitator for the groups.¹⁵ WG co-chairs are required to structure the activities and aims of the WG according to the template; the facilitator offered support and feedback to co-chairs to complete the Case Statement, especially in sections concerned with the more procedural aspects of WG activity (i.e., Work Plan section, Adoption Plan section, etc.).

Lesson learned: It is important to make clear to the group that the facilitator’s role in the Case Statement is not to co-author it; rather, it is to support and give pointers to improvement and, where possible, pre-empt any Community Review and/or TAB feedback.

Identifying Co-Chairs

One of the most significant challenges has been to work with WG proposers to identify individuals who are willing to take up the position of WG co-chair. For some groups, though the initial concept and aims of the WG put forward by the proposer(s) was well received and supported by those to whose work it would be relevant, it was difficult to persuade other individuals to become WG co-chairs. From the outset, the support available from RDA TIGER was used to make the co-chair role more attractive, with the point being made by the facilitator that it would allow co-chairs to focus more on the concept and aims of the WG rather than the organisational aspects; however, despite this, acting as a WG co-chair requires significant resource and attention, which those who were approached directly to take up the positions for different WGs made clear was not at their disposal.

Lesson learned: A large element of the facilitator support at the early stage of the WG is to work with the proposer(s) of the concept for the WG to identify and contact other potential co-chairs at the outset, giving them incentives and encouragement to co-chair the WG.

¹⁴ See Case Statement Development and Review Process: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/creating-and-managing-rda-groups/case-statement-development-and-review-process.html>

¹⁵ Research Data Alliance. (2022). RDA WG Template - Establishing an RDA Working Group (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00084>

Partner Engagement and International Engagement

This element is an essential part of starting an RDA WG. The concept has to be circulated early on as a draft and getting consensus from a number of potential group participants is the only route to a successful group. The facilitator has a huge role here, leaning on the Landscape and Communications services, RDA networks and other contacts to give suggestions to the WG proposer(s)/co-chair(s) about relevant individuals and organisations to engage from the outset. Some groups will be more mature in the commitment and buy-in from the community, some less. In many cases, the original concept for the WG has been formulated at a regional basis so the facilitator has to make clear that a diverse group of participants is necessary and has to make best efforts to identify potential co-chairs from different regions of the world.

Lesson learned: Circulate the WG concept early on and ensure to leverage the RDA's global network to identify early on international participants for the group.

Monitoring of Effort and Capacity

Every group is different in approach and some WG co-chairs/proposers have more experience of RDA procedures; as such, it is only natural that some groups will require more intensive input at different stages of their life-cycles. This makes it a challenge for the facilitator to gauge at the outset how much time to devote to each stage of the WG life-cycle. As a contingency, the team has set up a table to log 'actual' time spent on each WG, compared to 'planned' input. Input of each step to Asana is also an extra step for each Facilitator, although this helps hugely when it comes to allocating effort for future WGs. Each pilot group has different needs; however, one commonality was that each group welcomes proactive meeting organisation and minute-taking. This could be added to the facilitator brief for any future support offered to RDA Groups after the TIGER project.

Lesson learned: The facilitator is not a WG co-chair. This is a critical element of the service support, and the work has to be done by the co-chairs, although they often have limited capacity themselves. The facilitator should make this clear at the outset. The RDA TIGER team should consider whether to add meeting organisation and minute-taking to the facilitator brief.

Overall Insights on the Pilot Groups

A number of insights can be highlighted and the pilots are useful 'incubator' for the services and has helped to move to the next stage of onboarding Working Groups.

Lesson learned: The pilots have been an excellent instrument to trial and develop the services as well as to engage the community. RDA TIGER has reached the end of the first year and three of the four services are now in the roll-out stages. We can continue to carry out iterative self-reflection of the services as well as getting ongoing feedback from the groups in order to optimise these services.

